

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH A SOMATIC COMPONENT IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Phraseology is an interesting but insufficiently studied field of linguistics. In the works of V.V. Vinogradov [1], N.M. Shansky [2], A.V. Kunin [3-5] and others. contains definitions of phraseology. The object of linguists' study is phraseological coalitions or idioms, as well as phraseological unities. Phraseological units are able to recreate the peculiarity and originality of the national language, because they are its "mirror". The study of phraseology allows you to achieve a high culture of speech and expands your linguistic horizons. The ability to correctly apply phraseological units makes speech expressive, diverse and interesting for the interlocutor. The human world is fully reflected in phraseological units.

Somatic ("soma" – from the Greek lang. "body") phraseological units are found in all languages and represent the largest groups. These are phraseological units that contain the name of any part of the human body.

The aim of this article is to identify similarities and differences in the use of somatic phraseological units in English and Uzbek culture, as well as to identify the main ways of translating the studied somatic phraseological units. The study of the processes of the emergence and use of phraseological units, including a somatic component in English and Uzbek, helps to understand the national peculiarities of thinking and behavior of native speakers. Somatisms from phraseological Uzbek and English languages were taken as the research material.

Currently, the somatic vocabulary associated with the names of human body parts, including somatic phraseology, is becoming the subject of close attention of linguists due to the fact that difficulties arise in the search for tolerant intercultural communication.

Uzbek phraseological units, reflecting elements of culture, are associated with many areas of human life. At the same time, they can be connected both with the everyday empirical experience of the people, with their way of life, and with the sphere of material culture, with the historical experience of the people, etc. Comparative analysis of phraseology is of great interest for the study of common and distinctive features of the languages under consideration. The question of phraseology is relevant because to this day, despite numerous works, some aspects of the study of this section of the science of language remain controversial.

Phraseological units are one of the main units of the language, carrying national cultural elements. Comparing the phraseological units of the English and Uzbek languages helps to identify the different values inherent in these peoples, and plays an important role in the development of anthropocentrism, one of the main paradigms today. The vocabulary of the Uzbek and English languages differs, first of all, in that these languages belong to genetically different families. Although Uzbek is typologically included in the Altai language family by many scientists as an agglutinative language, genetically it belongs to a group of Turkic languages that form a separate family. The basis of the lexical richness of our language is made up of common Turkic and Uzbek words

To analyze the data obtained, we studied the meanings of the most commonly used somatisms in the explanatory dictionaries of the English and Uzbek languages and identified the meanings of these somatisms in phraseological units. The head in English is a part of the body through which emotions are conveyed in phraseological units (hang your head (surrender); hang one's head down. In addition, the head represents reason and thinking and indicates the presence or absence of mind and prudence (to have a clear head; keep a clear head). With the help of the head, we express the ability to concentrate (not to lose our heads; to keep one's head). The head also conveys a sign of superiority (hold your head high; carry one's head high).

- **uzb.:** bosh og'rig'i – ortiqcha tashvish; **eng.:** headache-excessive anxiety,
- **uzb.:** boshi osmonga yetmoq – xursand bo'lmoq; **eng.:** raised head high
- **uzb.:** bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmoq – hamjihat bo'lmoq, yakdil bo'lmoq; **eng.:** become like-minded people.
- **uzb.:** bir boshini ikki qildi – oilali qildi; **eng.:** made a head two - made married;
- **uzb.:** bir boshdan – boshlanishidan, tartib bilan; **eng.:** one head-to-head, from beginning to end, in order.
- **uzb.:** bosh egdi – itoat qildi, bo'ysundi; **eng.:** bowed down-obeyed.
- **uzb.:** bosh qo'shdi – aralashdi, qatnashdi; **eng.:** connected-intervened, participated.
- **uzb.:** bosh qotirdi – astoydil o'yladi, chuqur fikrladi; **eng.:** worked with head-thought hard, I thought deeply.
- **uzb.:** boshlarini bir joyga qovushtirdi – oila qurdi; **eng.:** put their heads together - created a family.
- **uzb.:** boshi bilan sho'ng'ib ketdi – butunlay berilib ketdi; **eng.:** left head - completely obsessed.
- **uzb.:** boshi ko'kka yetdi – behad sevindi; **eng.:** head reached up to the sky - incredibly happy
- **uzb.:** boshi yostiqa yetganda – kasal bo'lib qolganda; **eng.:** when the head reaches the pillow, when it hurts.
- **uzb.:** boshi oqqan tomon – duch kelgan taraf; **eng.:** the side where the head looks - where have to go.
- **uzb.:** boshi osmonda – nihoyatda xursand; **eng.:** head in the sky-incredibly happy
- **uzb.:** boshida danak chaqdi – ortiq darajada azoblandi; **eng.:** to chop nuts on the head is to suffer a lot.
- **uzb.:** boshidan oshib yotibdi – ortiq darajada, benihoya ko'p; **eng.:** above the roof – to a greater extent, insanely much.
- **uzb.:** boshdan oyoq – bus-butun, to'la-to'kis; **eng.:** from head to toe-whole, full.
- **uzb.:** boshiga ko'tardi I – qattiq shovqin qildi; **eng.:** raised it on head made a loud noise.
- **uzb.:** boshiga ko'tardi II – yuksak darajada izzat-hurmat qildi; **eng.:** raised on head II – highly glorified-respected.
- **uzb.:** boshiga qilich kelsa ham – har qanday sharoitda ham; **eng.:** even if a sword comes to mind – under any circumstances.
- **uzb.:** boshiga yetdi – halok qildi; **eng.:** reached head - ruined it.
- **uzb.:** bosh aylantirdi – esankiratdi; **eng.:** twisted head, fooled around.

Head – **uzb.** bosh - controls our thinking and consciousness. To have a good head for something – to have a clear head – boshi tiniq, to have a good head on one's shoulders – have your head on your shoulders – **uzb.** elkasida boshini ko'tarib yuribdi. And the absence of mind is transmitted in English as cabbage-head, wooden head, be soft in head, and in Uzbek – savdoi. Idioms can also express a person's ability to lose his will: to lose one's head – hang his nose, hang his head – **uzb.** boshini egdi, to bury one's head – bury his head in the sand – **uzb.** boshini ko'mib oldi. The component "head" in Uzbek and English languages also has the meaning of "life": to pay with your head / answer with your head / pay with your head – **uzb.** boshi bilan javob beradi. It should be noted that sometimes the "head" component, used in idioms in English and Uzbek languages, is perceived as a "mind" component. For example, to puzzle over something - to cudgel one's brains over something – **uzb.** bosh qotirmoq. Brain like a sieve-brainless, reckless, stupid – forgets everything about those who have a very bad memory. All Brawn and no brain-there is strength and no mind, **uzb.** miyasi teshik tog'ora, they do not judge a fool, which means there is strength – you must be able, **uzb.** kuch bor-aql kerak emas.

These discrepancies are the result of reflecting the national spirit, extralinguistic factors and linguistic connections within the system. At the same time, it is possible to note more similar meanings of idioms with somaticisms in English and Uzbek. This can be explained by their connection with the history of the development of peoples, which is reflected in the national identity of their mentality, language and culture. The explanation of the coincidence of the meanings of somatic phraseological units in English and Uzbek can be found not only in borrowings, but also in the patterns that cause the appearance of similar phraseological units.

In conclusion, I would like to note that as a result of the study of phraseological units, it would be appropriate to compile a dictionary of Uzbek and English somatic phraseological units. The studied subject is necessary for the successful mastery of the Uzbek language by foreign students and for the practice of translation from Uzbek into English and vice versa. Summing up, we note that the semantics of somatic phraseological units is directly related to a person, his perception of the world and attitude to reality. The comparison and analysis of phraseological units with somatic meaning in English and Uzbek languages revealed both general patterns and the national originality of phraseology, which in turn reflects the realities of life, culture and history of the English and Uzbek peoples. Our research does not exhaust the problems of the topic under consideration.

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